

PLAN FOR DISSEMINATION & EXPLOITATION INCLUDING COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES DELIVERABLE 6.1 – VERSION 1

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5	Skyhaus BVBA	ML6	Belgium
6	Suomen Biotaitteen Seura Ry	FBAS	Finland
7	Biofaction KG	Biofaction KG	Austria
8	Lantana Bio	Lantana Bio	France
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document gives an overview of the consortium's plan for dissemination, exploitation and communication of the activities performed within the deCYPher project, focusing on the development of a standardised platform implementing artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques to functionally achieve the oxygenation of plant metabolite scaffolds mediated by cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYPs). This plan aligns with FAIR and open science principles, emphasising the importance of openness and responsible use of intellectual property. Core communication messages focus on the impact of the integration of AI and ML and biotechnology to successfully improve the bio-based production platform. Additionally, this plan identifies key stakeholders that will be the target of the proposed dissemination, exploitation and communication activities.

ABBREVIATIONS

AI = Artificial intelligence
CYP = Cytochrome P450 enzyme
DBTL = Design-build-test-learn
DT = Digital tool
FAIR = Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
FTO = Freedom-to-operate
GA = Grant Agreement
KER = Key exploitable result
KPI = Key Performance Indicators
InBio = Industrial Biotechnology
IPR = Intellectual property rights
MCF= Microbial cell factory
ML= Machine learning
NGO = Non-governmental organization
OA = Open Access
OS = Open Science
PDEC = Plan for Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication
ROL = Results Ownership List
SynBio = Synthetic Biology
TG = Target group

CONTENTS

Deliverable factsheet	2
Project consortium	2
Executive Summary	3
Abbreviations	3
1 Preface	5
2 identification of key stakeholders	6
3 Dissemination strategy	8
4 Communication measures	11
4.1 Internal Communication	11
4.1.1 Main objectives for internal communication	11
4.1.2 Materials for internal communication	12
4.1.3 Internal communication channels	12
4.2 External Communication	13
4.2.1 Main objectives for external communication	13
4.2.2 Defining the audience	13
4.2.3 Key messages	14
4.2.4 External communication channels	15
4.2.5 Materials for external communication	16
4.2.6 Visual identity	21
4.3 Phases and Timing	23
5 Exploitation roadmap	25
5.1 Exploitation objectives	25
5.2 Identification of KERs	25
5.3 IPR Management	26
5.4 IPR assessment	27
5.5 Patent landscape evaluation	28
5.6 Exploitation strategy	29
6 Monitoring and evaluation: measuring impact	30
6.1 Performance metrics	30
6.2 Stakeholder receptivity	30
7 Conclusion	31

1 PREFACE

DeCYPher is an interdisciplinary project aiming at developing a standardized platform in which artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) techniques are implemented to overcome the main current hurdles in industrial biotechnology. As a proof-of-concept, this platform will be applied to enable the bio-based production of secondary plant metabolites, more specifically microbial production of oxygenated terpenoids and flavonoids. Using the AI platform, the mechanisms of action of cytochrome P450 enzymes (CYPs) responsible for the oxygenation of plant metabolite scaffolds will be studied, identified, implemented, and optimized to achieve functional microbial CYP expression resulting in a Microbial Cell Factory (MCF) that can be implemented in the bioproduction process of oxygenated plant metabolites. Altogether, deCYPher combines AI/ML and synthetic biology in the Design-Build-Test-Learn (DBTL) cycle to achieve transparent, reproducible, and modular biotechnology process development and optimization, supporting the European Green Deal and the circular economy.

More specifically, deCYPher sets out to:

- Implement artificial intelligence to explore, understand and develop sustainable biotechnology applications within safe planetary boundaries.
- Develop economically viable and sustainable production processes for oxygenated plant metabolites.
- Expand our insights and understanding on the societal impact of combining AI/ML and synthetic biology for industrial biotechnology applications.

We identify four key areas that make up the project's pathway to impact:

1. **Technological impacts:** (1) A standardized AI/ML pipeline implementing AI/ML into all steps of the DBTL cycle and across all steps in the biotechnology value chain that will generate opportunities for process optimization for the entire biotechnology sector. (2) The development of superior oxygenated plant metabolite microbial cell factories through the bioprospecting, localization and optimization of cytochrome P450 enzymes.
2. **Economic impacts:** The development of superior oxygenated plant metabolite microbial cell factories will assist in meeting the increasing demand for these compounds for applications in, for example, pharmaceuticals, insecticides, food preservatives, phytonutrients, fragrances and flavors. Additionally, the standardized AI/ML pipeline will facilitate process optimization in the whole biotechnology sector.
3. **Sustainability impacts:** By creating innovative bio-based methods to produce oxygenated plant metabolites, the goal is to alleviate the overexploitation of endangered plant species, prevent soil degradation, and reduce competition for land and other resources. This approach promotes a more sustainable and efficient process that can easily be adapted to use locally available waste feedstocks.
4. **Societal impacts:** deCYPher aims to employ its findings to bridge science and society using citizen-based participatory research and innovation, and arts- and design-based methods and considerations. Doing so, it will create public awareness regarding AI/ML approaches in biotechnology, thereby paving the way for social acceptance on the implementation of the proposed technologies.

This document sets out the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan for the deCYPher project, covering communication activities, dissemination strategies and exploitation measures that are based upon ensuring open access publication, and adherence to Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) criteria. The plan adheres to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and open science principles. To match the evolving needs of the project, the plan will be reviewed across the project period, with modifications declared within respective Periodic Technical Reports.

2 IDENTIFICATION OF KEY STAKEHOLDERS

The following stakeholders have been identified as having an interest in or influence on the project's results and their dissemination. Additionally, a definition of the project's engagement goals for each and the required effort for their engagement is given. This serves as a reference for developing targeted dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities in the subsequent sections.

1. **Academia and Research community:** DeCYPher aims to inspire and raise the innovation commitments of researchers across biological, engineering, computing, social sciences and humanities, with a focus on early-stage researchers. To reach this aim, research results obtained during the project will be disseminated predominantly through academic channels. Engagement with early-stage researchers will be achieved by hosting workshops and other means.
2. **Policy Makers and Regulators:** Awareness will be raised by engaging stakeholders through workshops and events, as well as demonstrating proof-of-concepts, to foster a positive attitude towards the technologies implemented and developed during deCYPher. This will assist in paving the way for the development of policies and regulations that support their uptake.
3. **General Public:** The consortium will stimulate awareness, engagement and debate regarding the implementation of AI/ML in the biotechnology sector, its applications, risks, benefits and pathways to acceptance. To do so, the activities and results of the project will be communicated in lay terms on the digital platforms of the project.
4. **Industry:** The aim is to initiate collaborative research projects with relevant partners for maturing the technology towards market, enter into license agreements. To reach this, the consortium will ensure IPR potentials are assessed and in place where necessary, demonstrate proof-of-concepts, engage to scope opportunities and hurdles.
5. **Media and Press:** DeCYPher aims to foster positive media coverage in credible and reputable media outlet by preparing a press-pack for easy sharing of key messages, images and latest news regarding developments and results.

For a full list of identified target groups, see Table 1. This list, together with the so far identified companies and organizations, serves two-fold: on the one hand to identify which groups dissemination (as well as communication) actions are best targeted to (and subsequently how). On the other hand, it also serves as a first step in a **stakeholder mapping exercise**, which – in conjunction with feedback from the deCYPher advisory board – will allow us to identify and engage with a selection of stakeholders.

Based on the initial stakeholder mapping exercise, the project will develop a database with contacts of likely stakeholders. Based on this list, the project will conduct stakeholder engagement activities: two rounds of **stakeholder roundtables** with 12-20 participants are foreseen to facilitate contact and provide feedback for deCYPher's approaches and results. The events will present diverse points of stakeholder views, concerns, and opportunities to the consortium, as project partners will be involved and asked to participate. As the project plan foresees two iterations, there is room for a potential adaption of the work plan in order to accommodate useful suggestions, avoid potential pitfalls or engage with any presented opportunities.

Table 1: List of deCYPher target groups. AI = artificial intelligence, InBio = industrial biotechnology, ML = machine learning, NGO = non-governmental organization, SynBio = synthetic biology, TG = target group.

Target groups	
ACADEMIA	<p>TG1. Young scientists & engineers</p> <p>TG2. Digital scientific community: data scientists, AI/ML software developers, data stewards, infrastructure operators, etc.</p> <p>TG3. SynBio, InBio & biotechnology scientific community: bioengineers, biotechnologists, etc.</p>
SECTOR/INDUSTRY	<p>TG4. AI/data sector: ML6, Collibra, Genedata, etc.</p> <p>TG5. SynBio, InBio & biotechnology sector: pilot plants, Isobionics, Lantana, Ginkgo Bioworks, Dupont, DSM, Evolva, Evonik, BASF, etc.</p> <p>TG6. Flavours & fragrance sector: Isobionics, IFF, Givaudan, Sanofi, etc.</p> <p>TG7. Agriculture: Nuscience, Kemin, Biothalys, BASF</p> <p>TG8. Plastics sector: BASF, Avantium, Ineos</p> <p>TG9. Phytonutrients sector: Lantana, BASF, Cargill, DSM, Chr. Hansen, Kemin</p> <p>TG10. Pharmaceutical sector: Sanofi, Enantia, Johnson & Johnson, etc.</p>
SOCIETY	<p>TG11. Regulation (advisory) bodies like EFSA, IUCN, JRC, etc.</p> <p>TG12. NGO's like FBAS, Bio-art societies, etc.</p> <p>TG13. Society at large: flavonoid and terpenoid application users, consumers of bio-based products</p> <p>TG14. Media and journalists</p>

3 DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The principal aim of the dissemination activities of the project is to maximize the uptake and hence impact of the project results, by making them available and understandable to different audiences. To do so, these activities started at the beginning of the project and will last up to four years after the end of the project.

Scientific results will be disseminated as soon as possible through publications in high-visibility journals, at international conferences, professional network meetings, participatory workshops, and posts on the project website (www.deCYPhar.bio). All partners of the deCYPhar consortium will request approval by all other partners prior to any dissemination action. Additionally, each new dissemination activity will be evaluated for potential intellectual proprietary right that needs to be safeguarded and/or protected (see section 5). Moreover, no dissemination may take place if there are conflicts with any other obligation under the Grant Agreement (e.g. personal data protection, security obligations, etc.).

To promote the technologies and products (Key Exploitable Results – KERs) developed by the partners of the consortium and ensure good visibility, uptake and impact, the consortium will:

- comply with the legal requirements as set out in Article 17 and Annex 5 of the Model Grant Agreement regarding Open Access publication. Immediate open access will be provided, i.e. at the same time as the first date of publication of the result, through a trusted repository using specific open licenses and in compliance with the obligations as set out in article 17 of the Annotated Grant Agreement. Beneficiaries have allocated budgets to fulfill Open Access obligations.
- Use established platforms for hard- and wetware sharing (e.g. OpenWetware.org, ohwr.org, SEVA-DB, BCCM).
- make the results understandable by all (e.g. tailor the terminology and language to the audience).
- gather feedback to improve and tailor technologies and products (including dissemination materials such as guides, handbooks, policy briefs, training materials) to the needs of the user.
- generate market demand for the project technologies and political support.
- assess needs and demands for the project technologies.
- ensure that relevant results are shared with each stakeholder group or main target (actor) groups via the most appropriate channel and form.

The dissemination of the project results will be in line with the FAIR principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable, in collaboration with Task 5.1 (Data Management Plan).

In terms of the project, we expect substantial results to include:

- Generic and modular AI/ML pipeline for synthetic biology applications.
- Open-source standardized AI/ML digital tools (DTs) to improve the Design-Build-Test-Learn cycle of diverse bioindustry needs.
- (Meta)data standards for various synthetic biology data.
- Novel CYP enzymes identified.
- Functional targeting of CYP enzymes to the bacterial membrane.
- Biobased production of one selected terpenoid at relevant environmental conditions.
- Biosensor-based genetic circuits steered by CYP-induced stress.

“Dissemination tools” describe both dissemination materials as well as the dissemination channels used to publish or circulate these materials. It is important to note that, while dissemination focuses primarily on project results, there can be overlap in dissemination and communication. This can be seen in overlapping channel categories, incl. press releases or the policy brief (see section 5.2.5.), and also in

overlapping development of materials, such as slides and poster templates. Furthermore, all partners will be involved in a variety of dissemination actions planned throughout deCYPher's lifetime, a listing of which follows.

- **Press Releases:** As also mentioned further on under the "Communication" section, press releases will be prepared and published via consortium partners and their media contacts at strategic moments during the project's lifetime, e.g. after the launch, to communicate interesting results or events important to the project. Press releases serve communication and dissemination purposes and can be used to draw media attention, as well as provide policy makers or other stakeholders with bite-sized, engaging, and generally intelligible views into the project and its expected outcomes. The first project press release was published to commemorate the project kick off.
- **Conferences, workshops, and meetings:** Dissemination activities extend also to partners' participation, presentations, and posters at a variety of venues, including top conferences in AI/ML techniques, synthetic biology, metabolic engineering and biotechnology. A few examples include: SEED, Applied Synthetic Biology in Europe, Next-Generation Synthetic Biology, etc.

Beyond their contribution to deCYPher's stakeholder activities, consortium partners also hope to participate at stakeholder specific conferences and meetings, such as Crop innovation and business, EFIB, BIOKET, SynBioBeta, Bits in Bio, the International Conferences on Cytochrome P450, the European Congress on Biotechnology, Bioflavour, etc.

- **Publications:** Dissemination activities will also center around publications, more precisely the publication of scientific papers in high-impact open science journals, e.g., Nature journals, Science, NAR, FEMS journals, Metabolic Engineering, ACS Synthetic Biology, Artificial intelligence etc. As deCYPher adheres to Open Science (OS) principles, all partners will make sure that scientific publications follow Horizon Europe's open access (OA) policies.

Beyond scientific publications, the project foresees the publication of a book that provides a deeper reflection on the convergence of AI/ML and synthetic biology, including opportunities and risks. Led by FBAS and Biofaction, the book will also provide a space for reflections on the deCYPher's planned art-science collaborations.

- **Data and Training:** For further details on data management, please see D5.1, the data management plan. Training sessions for data management are part of the project plan. For dissemination to communities in research and industry at large, deCYPher will use established platforms for hard- and wetware sharing, e.g. OpenWetware.org, ohwr.org, SEVA-DB, BCCM. Data and research output not fit for domain-specific repositories will be made open in more generic ones such as Zenodo. As well best practices, workflows, and standards developed during the project will be added to relevant ELIXIR resources like e.g. RDMkit, FAIRsharing, and WorkflowHub.

In addition to sharing data and methodologies, the project also plans to have training sessions for young scientists, possibly to take place during summer school. These will also serve as basis to produce several video tutorials to be made publicly available.

- **Interaction with other relevant (Horizon Europe) projects:** deCYPher is committed to engaging with other relevant (EU funded) projects and international initiatives, where possible, to avoid duplication and profit from potential synergies. For instance, the Horizon Europe project iCULTURE attended and presented during deCYPher's kickoff meeting in September 2023. Another Horizon Europe project, called "Bioindustry 4.0", which deals with machine learning and digital twins in industrial biotechnology has invited deCYPher to present during its summer webinar session to take place August 29-30th, 2024. In addition, Bioindustry 4.0 will join with deCYPher in putting out a common call for and artist-in-residencies as well as organising related art-science workshops

A summary including key performance indicators of deCYPher's dissemination activities can be reviewed in Table 2.

Table 2: Summary of deCYPher's dissemination activities. KPI = key performance indicators, InBio = industrial biotechnology, SynBio = synthetic biology, TG = target group.

Media	Target Group	KPI (Key Performance Indicators)	Objective	Partner
Project Website with stakeholder section	Scientists (TG1-3), industry (TG4-10), regulators (TG11)	2-4.000 visitors/ year	Clear & easy to understand aims & results of project for stakeholders, summary in at least 6 main EU languages	Biofaction, all
Conference/industrial fair (e.g., EFIB, ASBE, BioFlavour)	Scientists (TG1-3), industry (TG4-10)	5 presentations & 8 posters by M48	Create awareness in scientific & industrial community, find additional collaborators and users	All
Scientific journals (e.g., NAR, ACS, SynBio, etc.)	Scientists (TG1-3)	>10 top-level OA scientific papers by M48	High impact papers demonstrating scientific excellence to community, attract more researchers to the field	All
ELIXIR services (e.g., RDMkit)	Scientists (TG1-3), industry (TG4-5)	>3 contributions by M48	Best practices will be added to RDMkit to enable community adoption of other users	VIB, BSC
Repositories & Registries (e.g., SEVA)	Scientists (TG1-3), industry (TG4-5)	submissions to >4 repositories by M48	Enhance reusability of data, models and tools, also after the project end	All
E-Book	Scientists (TG1-3), Policymakers (TG11)	1 e-book by M45	provide a broad reflection on the convergence of AI/ML and SynBio for InBio	Biofaction, FBAS, all
Industry placements	Young scientists & engineers (TG1)	2	Enable interdisciplinary experience & learning for young scientists & engineers	All
Training on data management	Consortium, Advisory Board	2 training sessions in Y1-Y2	Ensure adoption & usage of the FAIRDOM-SEEK data management platform	VIB
Training (e.g., summer school, tutorials)	Young scientists & engineers (TG1)	one summer school. 3-5 video tutorials	Enable learning for next generation scientists & engineers to empower young professionals beyond the project lifetime	All, Biofaction
Cluster activities	Related H2020 & HE projects, (inter)national projects, networks (TG1-5)	>8 cluster activities	Establish close collaboration & synergies with relevant projects/networks/initiatives at the European and national/regional level to share information and maximise the visibility of the project results.	All
Policy brief	Policymakers (TG11)	1	Outlines the objectives and strategies of the project within the regulatory landscape. Aid non-specialized audiences by providing clear, concise, and accessible information on how the project aims to influence and navigate regulatory frameworks.	All

4 COMMUNICATION MEASURES

Communicating about the project and its topics is key for ensuring that the project reaches as broad an impact in society as possible by fostering interest and acceptance amongst its key target audiences. The goals defined for communication should support reaching the overall goals of the project. Defining the strategic guidelines of communication, namely the vision, mission and communication goals, are needed for directing and monitoring the communication efforts completed within the project and evaluating the impact of these efforts.

The guidelines for the communication measures within deCYPher are the following:

- **Vision:** A society that recognizes the importance of the implementation of AI/ML approaches for transitioning into a bio-based economy in which microbial production plays a key role.
- **Mission:** To communicate deCYPher's activities to its target audiences in order to raise awareness on the implementation of AI/ML for the optimization of microbial cell factories for plant metabolites and, at the same time, maximize the project's impact.
- **Objectives:**
 - To create and implement a compelling narrative for deCYPher, including developing a distinctive project brand and unique selling propositions, to enhance its visibility among stakeholders and target audiences.
 - To build engaged communities around the project and sustain regular interaction with stakeholders through an active strategy across the project's own channels (social media, website, mailing) as well as through other available external channels (press, publications, events, etc.).
 - To inform on deCYPher's results and highlight the potential applications of the methodologies and technologies developed within the project, further enhancing their exploitation after the project is finalized.
 - To raise awareness on the application potential of a generic AI/ML pipeline for the optimization of microbial cell factories.
 - To promote the microbial production of oxygenated plant metabolites which deCYPher aims to optimize.
 - To highlight how European collaborations can promote innovation and positively impact European society.

In this section, the strategy on how and when to communicate internally (within the deCYPher consortium), and publicly and outwardly about the deCYPher project is given.

4.1 Internal Communication

4.1.1 Main objectives for internal communication

Good mutual communication is very important for the smooth running of the project. The main objective of the internal communication activities is to ensure efficient and organized communication amongst the consortium members of deCYPher, and to:

- interact with the consortium members.
- receive feedback from the consortium members.
- build a strong consortium community.

4.1.2 Materials for internal communication

The different materials and tools for internal communication in the deCYPher project are defined in the **Project Handbook** (deliverable D7.1 in WP Coordination and Management).

- **Monthly online meetings:** updates on the project progress, announcement of periodic reporting, etc. We have carried out monthly so-called “check-ins” to update ourselves about the work done in the different partner groups.
- **Consortium meetings and workshops:** Face to face meetings, usually as annual meetings or more focused workshops, are an ideal opportunity to get to know each other better and to discuss personally the different challenges, opportunities and technical details.
- **Templates:** we created several templates to communicate in a uniform way (progress reports, minutes of meetings, milestones, presentations, posters).

4.1.3 Internal communication channels

The internal communication channels are defined in the **Project Handbook** (deliverable D7.1 in WP Coordination and Management). We are using the following channels:

- The project **SharePoint** (Figure 1): a central point to safely store and handle project documents and to monitor deadlines.

Figure 1: Screenshot of deCYPher's SharePoint homepage

- **Telephone (or video) calls:** fast and personal.
- **Virtual meetings (MS Teams):** Board meetings, WP and Task meetings.
- **Chat groups (MS Teams):** quick and informal communication.
- **E-mail:** a more formal way of exchanging information.
- **GitHub:** sharing of code written by different partners.
- **DataHub:** sharing of all required metadata.
- **NextCloud:** exchange of data generated throughout the project.

4.2 External Communication

4.2.1 Main objectives for external communication

The objectives of deCYPhers communication activities include distributing information and engaging with the audience about the project and the results, hence to:

- enhance the project's visibility via branding and corporate identity of output.
- communicate on the project and its activities to a wide variety of stakeholders, including the general public.
- reach out to and interact with diverse communities, to receive feedback from them.
- generate market demand.
- stimulate interactions and collaboration with the scientific community.
- build support for future research and innovation.
- further increase of public awareness.
- inform decision-makers.

4.2.2 Defining the audience

The communication plan aims at reaching beyond the project's own community. Thus, the target audience is described in Table 3.

Table 3: Target audience for the communication efforts of deCYPhers.

Target group	Definition	Aims
Scientists	Experts in the topic or in related topics (European and local).	Inform about the project's aim and vision, to create visibility and impact. Receive feedback from the community. Stimulate participation in project activities.
Policy makers	People, especially in a government or political party, who decide on new policies.	Raise awareness on a specific topic. Provide policy recommendation.
Stakeholders	People and organizations who have a stake in the area of our project. This includes NGOs, professional networks but also other target groups in our table.	Mobilize stakeholder support. Multiplication of dissemination.
Industry and companies	Commercial entities that could apply the technology created in deCYPhers, ranging from start-ups to large companies.	Inform about new opportunities and markets, improve existing processes and generate market demand.
The general public	Everyone is part of the public, here we define those that do not primarily fall into one of the other categories.	Inform the public at large about the project activities, its outcome, expected outcomes and impact. Acquire feedback about the project's aim and ask them for advice for future flavonoid and terpenoid target molecules of interest. Generate market demand.

The media	Print, radio, TV and online media.	Increase EU funding visibility, help in multiplying the communication outreach.
Other EU projects	Research projects funded by the EU that have some thematic overlap with our project where we may find synergies.	Align research interests, eliminate barriers for future exploitation, ... Stimulate cooperation.

4.2.3 Key messages

The objectives of deCYPher's communication activities include distributing information and engaging with the audience about the project and the results. An overview of the key messages for each of the target groups is given in Table 4.

Table 4: Key messages for the different stakeholders and target audiences of the communication activities. AI = artificial intelligence, InBio = industrial biotechnology, ML = machine learning, NGO = non-governmental organization, SynBio = synthetic biology, TG = target group.

	Target groups	Relevance for deCYPher	Stakeholder's interest in deCYPher	Key messages
ACADEMIA	TG1. Young scientists & engineers	Research synergies and collaborations	Research synergies and collaborations	1) DeCYPher is conducting cutting-edge research with the aim of optimizing microbial production of secondary plant metabolites using a generic AI/ML pipeline. 2) The consortium is willing to collaborate with other projects and researchers.
	TG2. Digital scientific community		Bridging the gap between scientific research and its industrial application	
	TG3. SynBio, InBio & biotechnology scientific community			
SECTOR/INDUSTRY	TG4. AI/data sector	Implementation of the solutions developed by the project in practice and validation of their usefulness.	The AI/ML pipeline developed in deCYPher can greatly improve industry performance for the microbial production of oxygenated plant metabolites. This can lead to new business opportunities and jobs.	1) deCYPher is developing and testing an AI/ML pipeline that can help speed up the development of bio-based production processes, contributing to their competitiveness. 2) The production of oxygenated plant metabolites is currently hampered by several issues (low titres, lack of purity, high production cost, etc) that deCYPher aims to address.
	TG5. SynBio, InBio & biotechnology sector			
	TG6. Flavours & fragrance sector			
	TG7. Agriculture			
	TG8. Plastics sector			
	TG9. Phytonutrients sector			
	TG10. Pharmaceutical sector			
SOCIETY	TG11. Regulation (advisory) bodies	Strengthening policy support for the microbial production of interesting chemicals and associated R&D work. Citizens will be the direct beneficiaries of the technologies developed by deCYPher. It is however important that these new technologies are accepted by a broad audience for them to be implemented successfully.	Finding viable ways to transition from a fossil fuel-based economy into a bio-based one.	1) Our results indicate a need to adapt policies because implementing the AI/ML pipeline that will be developed during the deCYPher project will enhance the transition from a fossil fuel-based economy to a bio-based one. 2) Valuable chemicals can be produced starting from renewable resources instead of fossil fuel-based resources. The implementation of AI and ML for industrial biotechnology process optimization will contribute to their economical viability.
	TG12. NGO's		Microbial production of chemicals has significant environmental and economic benefits for the EU.	
	TG13. Society at large			
	TG14. Media and journalists			

4.2.4 External communication channels

For the execution of the present communication plan a multichannel strategy will be followed. The channels that will be used are the following:

- The **project website**: Our public project website <https://www.decypher.bio/> is the calling card of our project, where we post background information about our project including news items, graphics and videos.
- **Social media networks**: Given the international nature of the deCYPher project, social media is one of the most effective ways of communicating about the project topics to a wide international audience. It also serves the purpose of networking by facilitating direct contacts between the project and relevant stakeholder profiles, from the academic sector to the industry, among others. Below an overview of the social media networks deCYPher will use:
 - **Twitter**: We will use the consortium's existing personal and organisational Twitter accounts to post messages about deCYPher. Twitter can be a great tool to share real-time updates and news and to engage with a wider audience. The use of existing personal and organisational Twitter accounts can leverage the existing followers' base and amplify the project messages. Multiple accounts posting about the project from different angles (e.g. organisational, personal) can help to demonstrate the reach and impact of the project.
 - **YouTube**: This is our main venue for sharing our project videos, primarily via the Channel of our communication partner <https://www.youtube.com/c/Biofaction>
 - **Twitch.tv**: This can be used for live streaming events and workshops. Ususally the content is not saved for later thus creating an additional incentive to join the live event online. (e.g. via <https://www.twitch.tv/bioartsociety>)
 - **LinkedIn**: A dedicated LinkedIn page for deCYPher was created (see Figure 2). We have chosen this strategy because LinkedIn is a professional social network that can be highly effective for reaching a business-to-business (or B2B) audience, building business relationships, and sharing industry-specific content. It is most relevant to professionals or businesses; in which case a LinkedIn page could be an effective way to reach out to this audience. A dedicated LinkedIn page also allows for more targeted messaging and branding specific to the project, rather than being mixed in with personal or organizational content on other social media channels. See: <https://www.linkedin.com/showcase/decypher-bio>

Figure 2: Screenshot of the deCYPher LinkedIn Showcase page

4.2.5 Materials for external communication

A number of materials to present deCYPher and its findings will be created throughout the project. An overview of communication materials and different opportunities for outreach are given. This may be supplemented with further materials as communication needs arise.

- **Website content:** The website has the following structure:
 - Home (landing) page including a short summary of the project
 - About
 - Objectives & Innovations
 - Bio-based production
 - AI-based methodology
 - Partners
 - News (see Figure 3)
 - Contact

Over the course of the project lifetime, we will also add a Results section and add more information under the various sections. As the project progresses, we will update and further improve the content of the website. The colour code of the website corresponds to the logo.

News

deCYpher Art-Science Lab
MAY 31, 2024 | ANNOUNCEMENT, EVENT, SCIENCE
Our Finnish partners from the Bioart Society, are facilitating a day-long symposium in Espoo, Finland on 6th June 2024 as kick-off for our deCYpher Art-Science collaboration activities (with more info soon to come). This symposium brings together...
[read more](#)

New Project Video: Innovating Bioprocesses with Microbes and AI
MAY 29, 2024 | ANNOUNCEMENT, SCIENCE, SOCIAL MEDIA
We are thrilled to announce the release of the first video for deCYpher, "Innovating Bioprocesses with Microbes and AI", now available on YouTube. This clip provides an in-depth look at our innovative project, exploring the future of biotechnology...
[read more](#)

Unlocking the Secrets of Life: AI Protein Models Demystified
NOV 30, 2023 | SCIENCE, SOCIAL MEDIA
If you want to understand how artificial intelligence is being implemented in the field of biology, specifically with regard to proteins, go read this blogpost. It gives a brief overview of what proteins are, their characteristics and the...
[read more](#)

Figure 3: Screenshot of the News section of the deCYpher website

- **Blog Posts:** Short explanatory stories can convey information to newcomers in a fast way for those who want to know more about the technical aspects of our work. An example was published in November 2023 about ML approaches to predict protein structures, see <https://blog.ml6.eu/unlocking-the-secrets-of-life-ai-protein-models-demystified-f286b222d571> and Figure 4.

Medium 🔍 Search ✍ Write Sign up Sign in

Unlocking the Secrets of Life: AI Protein Models Demystified

 Medha Hegde · Follow
 Published in ML6team · 16 min read · Nov 15, 2023

👍 90 🔍 🔄 📄

Image created using Adobe Firefly

This blogpost is aimed at those who want to understand how artificial intelligence is being implemented in the field of biology, specifically with regard to proteins. We give a brief overview of what proteins are, their characteristics and the applications of protein engineering. The potentials of AI in this area are explored by giving an overview of current state-of-the-art models that are involved in solving various protein-related problems.

Introduction

What is a Protein?
Proteins are the essential building blocks of life and are omnipresent. More

Figure 4: Screenshot of our first blog post

- **Videos:** A video can explain more than a thousand words and complement our other text-based communication content. In May 2024 we published our first deCYPhەر video (Figure 5), titled “deCYPhەر Innovating Bioprocesses with Microbes and AI” and which can be found at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SalY-J9bAAU>.

Figure 5: Screenshot of our first deCYPhەر video, available on Youtube

- **Policy brief:** We will produce a policy brief that outlines the objectives and strategies of the project within the regulatory landscape. This brief will be designed to aid non-specialized audiences by providing clear, concise, and accessible information on how the project aims to influence and navigate regulatory frameworks.
- **Press Release:** We will issue several press releases to announce key milestones and achievements of the project. The press releases will be crafted to attract media attention and inform the public and relevant stakeholders about the project's goals, progress, and impact. It will highlight significant developments, partnerships, and outcomes in a way that is engaging and easy to understand, ensuring broad dissemination and increased visibility among both specialized and general audiences. For our first press release, see for example <https://www.ml6.eu/press/decypher-uses-ai-and-synthetic-biology-to-unlock-the-potential-of-rare-natural-compounds> or <https://www.biofaction.com/decypher-uses-ai-and-synthetic-biology-to-unlock-the-potential-of-rare-natural-compounds/> and Figure 6.

Figure 6: The press release was also promoted on social media, such as LinkedIn.

- **Meetings and workshops:** We will organize a number of meetings and workshops to discuss specific topics related to deCYPher with people from within and outside our consortium. One example was the so-called “deCYPher lab: on the ethics and aesthetics of linking AI/ML & SynBio” organised by the Finnish Bioart Society, one of deCYPher partners, in Helsinki in June 2024, featuring several speakers from the deCYPher consortium and speakers from other organisations. The event was open to the public and live streamed as well. See <https://bioartsociety.fi/projects/decypher/activities/decypher-lab-on-the-ethics-and-aesthetics-of-linking-ai-slash-ml-and-synbio> and Figure 7.

Figure 7: Photo of one of the panel discussions during the deCYPher lab workshop which was a hybrid event on June 6th 2024.

- **Citizen engagement events:** We will organise a series of citizen panels involving in total over 100 participants from at least 4 European countries (well distributed across Europe), who will first learn about the goals of deCYPher and then start to evaluate the societal impact of several flavonoid and terpenoid products. The societal impact will be measured according to the UN sustainability goals in terms of improved efficiency, climate change adaptation and sustainability of industrial processes in the bio-based sectors. The result will be a ranked list that will serve as a decision-making basis for the consortium to develop an open access methodology to produce 3-5 additional terpenoid and flavonoids targets. The open access methodology is meant to enable any company, university, government, NGO, or biohacking lab outside the consortium to produce the new targets themselves and contribute to the UN sustainability goals.
- **Graphics and Infographics:** We created a number of graphics to be used on our website, on social media and other presentations that allow for a better overview about our goals and the methods we use to achieve them. An example of an infographic for deCYPher is given in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Example of graphics used to communicate on deCYpher.

The following table (Table 5) summarized the communication target groups, channels and materials:

Table 5: The communication target groups for deCYpher.

Target group	Communication channels	Materials
Scientists and EU projects	The project website Social media networks (LinkedIn, Twitter) Science news portals	Video Events Infographic Press Release
Policy makers	The project website Social media networks (LinkedIn, Twitter)	Press releases Infographic Blog Posts

		Press Release
Stakeholders	The project website Social media Networks (LinkedIn & Twitter)	Video Events Infographic Blog Posts Press Release
Industry and companies	The project website Social media Networks (LinkedIn) Science news portals	Video Infographic Blog Posts Press Release
The general public and the media	The project website Social media Networks	Video Infographic Blog Posts Press Release

4.2.6 Visual identity

We have implemented a professionally designed and highly crafted project identity comprising logo, website theme, templates for print materials and multimedia presentations to develop and implement a strong narrative for the deCYPher project.

- **Color code and Logo:** At the start of the project, we issued a survey to all project partners asking the following questions:
 - What beliefs and values are important to the project group/project?
 - What makes the project group better than others?
 - What makes the deCYPher project special?
 - Who is the project aimed at, who is the target group?
 - What three words can be used to describe the project group/project?
 - What three words should be used to perceive deCYPher from the outside?

Based on the more than 40 answers we received we designed a number of Logo suggestions and different colour palettes. Eventually we decided on the following colour palette that brings together the sphere of artificial intelligence and synthetic biology (Figure 9).

Figure 9: Color code for deCYPher and AI-generated image with these colors.

Based on the color code, we created a logo that serves as a reference identity to be used in all dissemination, outreach and communication tasks (see Figure 10).

Figure 10: deCYPher Logo connecting the computer world (lower left) to the world of plants (upper right).

- **Presentation:** a PowerPoint presentation template was created to support all consortium members when they present deCYPher at conferences meetings etc. We also created templates for deliverables, milestones and exploitable results (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: Template/master PowerPoint file for presentations about deCYpher.

- Acknowledgement:** in all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities, an acknowledgement of EU funding will be published. Display the EU emblem (Figure 12) and include the following text (Disclaimer):

'Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.'

Figure 12: EU emblem to be displayed in all communication, dissemination and exploitation activities.

4.3 Phases and Timing

The principal aims of the communication activities are to make the project, its activities and progress visible and known to different target audiences. To do so, these activities have started before the beginning of the project, in its conceptualization phase, and will last until beyond completion as to ensure sustainability and maximize impact.

The focus of the communication actions will shift as the project advances. In the beginning, the emphasis will be on presenting the project to the various stakeholders. In the middle, on raising awareness of the topics and building an interested community around the project. In the end, the idea

is to maximise the impact of the project by communicating results and, if relevant, laying the groundwork for future exploitation of the project outcomes.

A summary including key performance indicators of deCYPher's communication activities can be reviewed in Table 6, and the planned timings and frequencies for communication activities in Table 7.

Table 6: Summary of communication activities. AI = artificial intelligence, KPI = key performance indicators, InBio = industrial biotechnology, ML = machine learning, SynBio = synthetic biology, TG = target group (see also Table 1).

Media	Target group	KPIs	Objective	Partner
Project Website with public section	Media and public (TG13 & 14)	5000-10.000 visitors/ year	Clear & easy to understand aims and results of project, summary in at least 6 main EU languages	Biofaction
Infographics	Media and public (TG13 & 14)	2-4.000/ year	Visual summary and abstract of deCYPher's goals, in at least 6 main EU languages	Biofaction
Social media (twitter, Youtube, Instagram)	Media and public (TG13 & 14)	250 subscribers per year, >30.000 impressions/year	Information feeds go via the Project Website to encourage sharing, create conversation, build interest audiences & establish the foundations for uptake communities.	Biofaction
Series of short film clips (Youtube)	Public (TG13)	500-3.000 views/ year	Raise awareness and present deCYPher as viable future technology bridging SynBio and AI/ML. Highlight socio-economic and environmental benefits, sustainability.	Biofaction
FAQ (and answers) list	Media and public (TG13 & 14)	2-4000/ year	Manage expectations, acknowledge concerns and request for more information, providing thoughtful answers, building trust in consortium.	Biofaction
Exhibition in art/design galleries	Public and Media (TG13 & 14)	500-1000 visitors in total	To introduce science as rich and fascinating area that can inspire art and be inspired by art.	FBAS, Biofaction
Workshop series and residencies	Artists and designers (via TG 12: NGOs)	3 direct participants for residencies	Stimulate several different practical applications of deCYPher tech in new and creative ways. Leverage potential of art and design influencers.	FBAS, Biofaction
Magazine articles	Regulation bodies, NGOs, public and media (TG11 – TG14)	5000-10.000 views by M48	Mainstream the deCYPher innovation, contextualise the benefit of the product, reduction of resources in the production process & address ethical questions	Biofaction, all

Table 7: Timing and frequencies of communication activities

Tools	Frequency	Timing
Website	Min. 2.000 visits /year	Start M3
Press release	Min. 4 press releases	M1, M12, M24, M48
LinkedIn	Min. 1 post per month	Start M3
Video	3 videos during the project lifetime	First Video before M12, second before M28, third video before end of project

5 EXPLOITATION ROADMAP

In this section, the exploitation roadmap and strategies that will be implemented in support of project exploitation efforts is given. This exploitation plan will guide project partners in exploitation activities, ensure transfer of project results while safeguarding Intellectual Property (IP) and help maximize the impact of project-developed results. To this end, it defines processes that will be implemented throughout the deCYPher project to:

- Identify Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
- Evaluate the different forms of protection available and determine the best option for each KER (on a case-to-case basis).
- Define the dissemination strategy of Results to safeguard the effective protection of IPR.
- Define the area and uses and the appropriate exploitation route for each KER

5.1 Exploitation objectives

The mid- and long-term exploitation of the outcomes of deCYPher are expected to be the following:

- **Scientific:** (1) A standardized platform to profoundly implement AI and ML techniques to overcome the current hurdles in InBio. (2) Characterized and functional application of the oxygenation of plant metabolite scaffolds mediated by CYPs, with the aim of optimizing the microbial cell factory and, ultimately, the bioproduction process.
- **Economic:** (1) DeCYPher aims to create new business opportunities for AI/ML services and consultancy SME's that enable implementation of the 'learn' module into the InBio and life science sector. (2) A more regular supply of oxygenated plant metabolites produced in a more economically viable way when compared to the production methods in place before the start of the project.
- **Societal:** The development of new bio-based production methods will have a positive societal impact by reducing the overexploitation of endangered plant species, soil degradation, and competition for land and other resources and to enable a more sustainable and efficient process that can be easily adapted to locally available (waste) feedstocks.

5.2 Identification of KERs

To ensure impact and value from our activities, deCYPher integrates knowledge & data management and transfer plans to collect, transfer, and use all relevant project knowledge.

Key Exploitable Results will be identified through the recording on a continuous basis throughout the project period of all results (de-novo discoveries, new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge) in an internal template with detailed descriptions to determine the results' potential and ensure they reach users who can benefit. For each KER, the expected TRL level at project completion will be declared, the value proposition of the KER defined, target market specified and the specific IPR/Open science strategy to be used will be stated.

deCYPher PROJECT RESULTS

Exploitation template

Project	
Project number	101081782
Project name	deCYPher
Project acronym	deCYPher

To ensure impact and value from our activities, deCYPher integrates knowledge & data management and transfer plans to collect, transfer, and use all relevant project knowledge.

All project RESULTS (de-novo discoveries, new methodologies/processes, adaptations, insights, alternative applications of prior know-how/knowledge) will be recorded in an internal template (following pages) with detailed descriptions as the first step in this process. Your responses will help us determine RESULTS' potential and ensure they reach users who can benefit.

We want to emphasise that you can share your RESULTS here without compromising intellectual property (IP) or affecting your publication potential later.

If you have troubles with terminology in this document, please take a look at definitions at the end.

Figuur 13: Screenshot of the template used for the identification of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) during deCYPher.

5.3 IPR Management

The obligations towards intellectual property rights (IPR), access rights and rights of use are described in art 16 and Annex 5 of the GA. Beneficiaries must — up to four years after the end of the action - use their best efforts to exploit their results. If, despite a beneficiary's best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the project, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the EC) use the Horizon Results Platform to find interested parties to exploit the results. Applications for patents, trademarks, registered designs, utility model etc., are being listed in the continuous reporting module on the EU Funding & Tenders Portal.

Effective exploitation of the key exploitable results (KERs) depends upon, amongst other issues, the proper management of intellectual property, which should be part of the overall management of knowledge in the project.

Throughout the deCYPher project, specific actions have been, and will continue to be, undertaken for addressing the issues related to intellectual property rights. These include the pre-existing knowledge (Background) of the project partners, an assessment of the results generated during the project, proposals for the optimal protection of IPR, and ownership and proper implementation of IPR protection measures.

The framework of the IPR management is set out within the Consortium Agreement, which stipulates the rules related to the following IP issues:

- Identification of the Background and the specific limitations and conditions for its implementation;
- Ownership of the results;
- Transfer of the results;
- Access rights to the Background and the results;
- Non-disclosure of the information.

Participants will assess the possibility of protecting their results once these are generated. Beneficiaries are free to choose any available form of protection of intellectual property. The choice of the most suitable form of IP protection, as well as the duration and geographical coverage, depends upon the results (e.g. if it is an invention, software or a database), and the business plans for their exploitation and legitimate interests of consortium partners.

To clarify ownership of the KERs obtained during the course of the project, a Results Ownership List (ROL) will be drawn up and submitted in the last reporting period. This ROL must contain information on who is the owner of the results, whether the ownership is single or joint, the country of establishment, and whether the results will be exploited by the owner or if ownership of results has been transferred and if so, to whom. The listed owner in the ROL will be responsible for the exploitation and reporting obligations of their results after the project ends.

5.4 IPR assessment

The deCYPher consortium will evaluate and select the most appropriate intellectual property right protection on a case-by-case basis for each key exploitable result that will be identified during the project. An overview of the different potentially relevant safeguarding measures is given below in Table 8.

Table 8: Overview of different potentially relevant safeguarding measures for intellectual property right protection

Protection Measure	Description	Coverage	Duration
Patent	Grants the inventors exclusive rights to make, use, sell, or distribute the invention in exchange for its public disclosure.	Covers for example products, processes, machines, and compositions of matter.	Typically 20 years from the filing date.
Copyright	Grants the creator exclusive rights to use and distribute their work.	Applies to literary, musical, artistic, and certain other intellectual works including software.	Lasts for the life of the author plus 70 years.
Trademark	Protects symbols, names, and slogans used to identify and distinguish goods and services in the marketplace.	Covers logos and symbols, brand names, phrases and slogans, designs and shapes.	Lasts indefinitely as long as they are in use and properly maintained.
Trade secret	Confidential business information providing a company with a competitive edge.	Includes formulas, practices, processes, designs, instruments, patterns or any other information that is not generally known or readily accessible.	Lasts indefinitely if kept confidential.
Industrial design	Safeguards the visual design of objects that are not purely utilitarian.	Covers the ornamental or aesthetic aspects of a product, including its shape, configuration, pattern or color.	Typically ranges from 10 to 25 years, often subjected to renewal.

Utility model	Similar to a patent, but more focused on incremental innovations and improvements in the functional aspects of devices and processes.	Covers mechanical devices, product improvements, and processes.	Typically lasts 7-10 years, without the possibility of extension.
Geographical indication	Protects products with a specific geographical origin and a reputation linked to a specific location, aiding to maintain the authenticity and cultural heritage of these products, and providing economic benefits to the regions producing them.	Applies to products with a close link to a geographic area.	Indefinitely if the product and the link to the origin are maintained.

5.5 Patent landscape evaluation

Patent landscape evaluation is necessary not only to scope the potential for IPR measures to be implemented in relation to project results, but to also test the novelty of proposed outcomes to ensure pathways for exploitation. A number of patent evaluation measures will be utilised by the consortium. These can include:

1. **Patent Searches:** Utilisation of patent databases using keyword searches and utilisation of patent classification systems to identify relevant patents. An initial drafting of keywords for performing the keyword search are: *Cytochrome P450, Cytochrome P450 reductase (CPR), Transmembrane domains, Membrane targeting, Bio-based flavonoid/terpenoid production, Microbial flavonoid/terpenoid production, genetically engineered microbial cell factories, Synthetic biology and artificial intelligence/machine learning*
2. **Freedom-to-operate (FTO) Analysis:** With this measure we will determine if there are existing patents that could pose a risk to the freedom to operate in a specific market and analyse their claims to understand the scope of protection.
3. **Patent Landscape Analysis:** An evaluation of the patent portfolios of market actors will be conducted to understand strengths, weaknesses and scope of protection against the various KERs determined by the consortium throughout the project.
4. **Prior Art Searches:** These will be conducted predominantly through scientific literature such as academic journals, conference proceedings and other scientific literature for determining the relevant prior art.
5. **Infringement Analysis:** We will assess the proposed technologies to determine if they might infringe upon existing patents and the potential risks of infringement.
6. **Collaboration and Networking:** Conferences and networking events will be attended to stay informed about the latest developments in the field. The available resources of Technology Transfer Offices, available to a number of partners, can be enhanced through collaboration with intellectual property attorneys and experts for in-depth assessments.
7. **IPR Training:** The consortium will seek training opportunities on basic intellectual property principles and the landscape of available IPR safeguarding measures, including their scope, applicability, effort in implementation and protection duration.

8. **Continuous Monitoring:** We will regularly review and update the rapidly evolving technological and market landscape and monitor the patent activities of key actors. Continuous monitoring will also be implemented through the use of IP watch services to provide regular notification on newly filed patents and changes in the patent landscape.

Through the use of these measures, the consortium will be better positioned to understand the potentials and risks surrounding IPR, the appropriate measures to consider for any given outcome and be informed on the rapidly developing landscape.

5.6 Exploitation strategy

The first step for developing the appropriate and comprehensive exploitation strategy is to identify the list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) to be developed in the deCYPher project. At the stage of proposal submission, various example types of KERs (digital tool, digital infrastructure, product, synthetic biology tool, and scientific) and their potential means of protection and exploitation were identified (Table 9).

Table 9: Potential means of protection of the different types of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) as identified at the stage of proposal submission. AI = artificial intelligence, DT = digital tool, IP = intellectual property.

Type of KER owner	Protection	Area and uses
Digital tool (DT) <i>ML6, BSC</i>	>3 open source DTs, other DTs patented	AI and data: (i) boost research & innovation, (ii) licensing patents to other life science sectors
Digital infrastructure <i>VIB, BSC</i>	Open source software	AI and data, life science: boost research & innovation
Synthetic biology tool <i>CSIC, Isobionics, Lantana, UGent, WR</i>	Patents <u>Parts, tools:</u> individual IP <u>Strains:</u> joint IP	Synthetic Biology, (Industrial) Biotechnology: (i) licenses to spinouts or other companies (e.g., from Advisory Board), and (ii) boosting future research & innovation
Scientific <i>Isobionics, Lantana</i>	Patents, trade secret <u>Process:</u> individual IP	Flavonoid and/or Terpenoid producers: further upscaling & commercialisation of flavonoids by Lantana and terpenoids by Isobionics
Product	Knowledge/patents	Synthetic Biology, (Industrial) Biotechnology: (i) boost re-search & innovation, (ii) licenses for other biotech applications

The list of preliminary exploitation plans per KER will be updated throughout the deCYPher project to ensure that the widest communication and dissemination of the results generated by deCYPher can be achieved, protected and exploited. On the submission date of the first version of this PDEC, seven KERs were identified which will be followed up on.

Beyond the project lifetime, each partner will implement measures which will be defined to ensure the exploitation of its results (either directly or indirectly) by one or more of the following methods:

- Using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- Developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- Creating and providing a service.

6 MONITORING AND EVALUATION: MEASURING IMPACT

This PDEC is a living document which serves as the main guide for the project's dissemination, exploitation and communication actions. The plan will be revised regularly and modified when necessary. Planned revisions are scheduled for each year of the project.

Dissemination, exploitation and communication and their impact will be continuously monitored over the project period. In response to this monitoring, the project partners will adapt the dissemination, exploitation and communication actions and strategies when necessary, always keeping the mission, vision and objectives in sight.

Below we outline the key performance metrics for the various activities together with the measures for assessing stakeholder receptivity.

6.1 Performance metrics

Both qualitative and quantitative ways of measuring dissemination, communication and exploitation efforts and impact will be applied. An overview is given in Table 10.

Table 10: Overview of qualitative and quantitative ways of measuring dissemination, communication and exploitation efforts and impact.

Tools	Indicator	Objective (examples)	Measuring instrument
Website	Number of visits	5000 – 10.000 visitors/year	Host (one.com) analytics
Press release	Number of news articles based on press release	1.000 people reading/press release	Project archive
LinkedIn	Number of followers	Min. 1 post per month / 250 followers	To check LinkedIn connections and 'likes'
Video series	Number of views	500 views/video	Checking YouTube and related view statistics (e.g. if embedded in LinkedIn)
Workshops / Summer school	Number of trainings / summer school	Min. 2 training session and 1 summer school	Regular reporting on dissemination activities by project partners
Policy brief	Number of papers published	Min. 1	Regular reporting by project partners
Scientific Publication	Number of scientific publications published	min 10	Regular reporting on dissemination activities by project partners
Art-science Exhibition	Number of visitors, both physical and online	Min 150	Counting visitors

6.2 Stakeholder receptivity

Stakeholder receptivity indicates their willingness to support, adopt, or collaborate and is crucial for the successful adoption of project results. Measuring stakeholder receptivity involves assessing the level of acceptance, engagement, and responsiveness of various stakeholders. Below we identify a range of measures, with associated KPIs, through which the consortium will be able to gauge receptivity.

- **Social media monitoring:** We will monitor social media platforms for mentions, comments, feedback etc. and discussions related to the project, assessing the stakeholder group and the tone of interactions to gauge stakeholder sentiment.

Associated KPIs:

- Quantification of mentions, comments, likes, reposts, shares.
 - Growth of audience, broken down, if possible, into stakeholder categories
 - Reach of posts, mentions and shares
- **Stakeholder round tables:** Two rounds of stakeholder roundtables will be planned specifically dedicated to discussing stakeholder perspectives.

Associated KPIs:

- Level of attendance and participation rate
- Feedback for more information

7 CONCLUSION

This document has outlined the Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication plan for the deCYPher project. Activities, measures and KPIs have been defined. Stakeholders have been identified for targeting these measures. The project will comply with Open science principles, and Open Access requirements will be adhered to. A comprehensive plan for IPR assessment has been defined. These measures will facilitate the successful dissemination, exploitation and communication of the project.